

Flexible Work Arrangement and Employee Performance in Food and Beverage Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study main aim is to investigate the relationship between flex work arrangement and employee performance of food and beverage firms in Rivers state. The specific objectives are to investigate the relationship between job rotation and employee effectiveness, innovativeness and efficiency. The target population was employees from fifteen (15) food and beverage firms in Nigeria. This study adopted survey research design using qualitative approaches. On data analysis, diagnostic test was conducted along with descriptive statistics and statistical tool for empirical analysis was Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient to determine the level of relationship between the independent and dependent variables, partial correlation was used to determine the influence of the control variable (organizational culture) on employee performance. The sample size of the survey study was 224 questionnaires returned from the employees' respondents of the fifteen (15) selected food and beverage firms in Rivers state. The result showed that JR has low relationship with to employee effectiveness, innovativeness and efficiency. CW has a very strong relationship with employee effectiveness but has very low relationship with innovativeness and efficiency. The study recommended that managers should provide flexible work arrangements considerations such as employees flexibility on when to begin and end work as long as they meet the target since this influences performance.

Key Words: Flexible, Work Arrangement, Employee Performance, Food and Beverage, Firms

INTRODUCTION

Organizations seek to attain a high level of performance in her day to day operations and activities. To achieve these, firms always set several goals and objectives, and always seek to attract and retain highly qualified and motivated staff in order to effectively achieve these objectives. Allen (2021) opined that satisfied worker works harder and better and put in more efforts that helps to increase employee performance. Hence, firms try to create a satisfied staff for the well-being of the organization. Organization also try to create a pool of satisfied staff to ensure that hindrances are not placed on the way of employees to generously obligate themselves in the pursue of stated and or emergent organizational goals. However, the total employee performance depends on efficient and effective performance of discrete employees who work in an organization. Koys, (2021) opined that

it is crucial for firms to comprehend what employees exactly feel on their job and stage of satisfaction, as this can help improve business outcome and probably increase performance as well. However, employee performance rests on efficient and effective performance of discrete workers who work in an organization. An organization therefore, looks up to their staff performance to gain high performance. Flexible working arrangements are actually emerging issues in human resource management field. According to Cohen (2018), the world is becoming a global village; hence as an employee in any organization the balance between personal life and work responsibilities should not be ignored, if the employee performance is to be achieved.

For many employees today both male and female lives are becoming more consumed with a host of family and other personal responsibilities and interests in addition to demands of the workplace. There is therefore a perceived imbalance between the demands of current lives and people's abilities to adequately cope with them and this may lead to an experience of stress (World of Work Report., 2011). In a society filled with conflicting responsibilities and commitments, flexible work arrangement has become a predominant issue in the workplace. Three major factors contribute to the interest in and importance of serious consideration of flexible work arrangement: global competition, renewed interest in personal lives, family values and an aging workforce. Concerns have always been raised regarding policy and debates on flexible work arrangement from perspectives of the quality of working life when weighed against the broader family matters. However the challenge has been how employees would adopt good flexible work arrangement practices and the organizations to adopt policies to tackle conflicts that ensue from the interface of family or social pressures and work stress.

This study seeks to investigate the emerging issues in the relationship between work flexibility and employee performance. It shall examine the role of Job Rotation; flex time and part time in enhancing employee performance. Flexible working arrangements like flexible part time, shift work, compressed work hours and Job Rotation are often used to help employees in balancing their family and work life (Lim & Teno 2020) during 'core hours' which Shift work is a set of periods of working, often designed to provide 24-hour cover as a three-shift systems or sometimes operating as a two-shift system or a 'twilight shift' which lasts from say, 5 pm to 9 pm. Part-time work is where an employee's contracted hours are less than the standard full-time hours which can involve working only number of hours over any number of days. A temporary contract is employing extra staff on short-term contracts of varying length (weekly, monthly, and 6- monthly). Flexi-time is whereby a full time employee schedules his/her time so that at the end of the day he/she should have covered the number of our required of him to cover

Concept of Flexible Work Arrangement

According to Perrin (2021) flexible work schedules are important element of Organization strategies which should be geared towards retaining a motivated workforce. Flexible work practices have been practiced in both developing and developed countries and both employers and employees have benefitted from them. Rau and Hyland, (2022) define flexible work arrangement as an alternative to the standard working day. It usually comprehends to organizational initiatives which enhance

employees' flexibility on the time and place where work has to be accomplished, and also various policies exerting influence on the number of hours worked. Economic, technological, social and family changes have encouraged the introduction of flexible working arrangements. The flexibility arrangements includes; flex-time, absence autonomy, compressed work weeks, reduced schedule, telex-work, extra vacation days, limited schedule of meetings (meetings cannot be scheduled too late at the end of the day), flexible holidays and keeping with the schedule (employees work the mandatory 8 hours /day and do not extend their schedules longer).

Flexible work practices as stated by Hill, (2021) allow employees the freedom to work outside the standard work schedules. According to Rau, (2013) flexible work practices are different forms of working schedule that enables employees to work outside the normal work day. Some of various forms of flexible work practices include telecommuting, compressed hours, shift, flexi-time and annualized hours. However, this study was interested in only four types of flexible work practices namely: telecommuting, compressed work week, Job Rotation and flexi-time.

Concept of Employee Performance

Firm performance is the outcome achieved in meeting internal and external goals of a firm. Performance has several outcomes including growth, survival, success and competitiveness. Better performing employees at work become more committed to their organizations and ultimately contribute to increased organizational performance as well as growth of the economy. Marko and Sridevi (2020) measured that well performing employees are considered with high motivation and values to ensure positive outcome in their organization. In addition, they thought of wellbeing of employees is an acknowledgement to his contribution for organization performance. Markos and Sridevi, (2020) also confirmed that engagement is a double side of sharing information between managers and employees and find out the weaknesses of employee that need attention. Consideration of top management to employees' satisfaction is a lead towards organization performance.

Sinha (2021) opined that organizational performance depends on the willingness and also the openness of the employees themselves on doing their jobs. He also stated that by having this willingness and openness of the employees in doing their job, it could increase the organizational productivity which also leads to the performance. Stup (2013) stated that to have a standard performance, employers have to get the employees task to be done on track as to achieve the bank's goal or target. By having the work or job done on track, employers could be able to monitor their employees and help them to improve their performance. Furthermore, a reward system should be implemented based on the performance of the employees. This is to motivate the employees in order to perform more on their task. There are several factors that being described by Stup (2013) towards the success of the employees' performance. The factors are such as physical work environment, equipment, meaningful work, performance expectation, feedback on performance, reward for good or bad system, standard operating procedures, knowledge, skills and attitudes.

Employee Effectiveness

Any definition is a function of who is defining or who is evaluating effectiveness and why he or she is doing so. As there are problems with its meaning, so also are there problems with the measures because each perspective introduces a different dimension to the meaning. Other problems with the issue of organisational effectiveness as enumerated by Koys (2012) include the criteria for its identification and the best models to guide research and practice. There is no single criterion to measure effectiveness. There is no agreement among the experts as to its meaning and indicators; some measures contradict each other, say for example, is it more rewards to shareholders or more compensation to employees? At times, the system is very complex with many wanted and unwanted by different constituents, making a unitary view of effectiveness inadequate and unrealistic. Effectiveness is also a function of the internal function, dynamics and values of any given organisation and each organisation runs its affairs in such a way it believes will lead to effectiveness (Miller, 2016).

Innovativeness

Employee engagement is arguably the most critical metric for organizations in the 21st Century. Employee engagement is directly influenced by growth of the organization, value addition experienced by employees and employee perception of the organization. HR practitioners believe that the engagement challenge has a lot to do with how employee feels about the about work experience and how he or she is treated in the organization (Perrin, 2021). It has a lot to do with emotions which are fundamentally related to drive bottom line success in a company. Employee engagement Innovativeness has a direct impact on the organization's productivity. The concept of engagement has naturally evolved from past research on high involvement, empowerment, job motivation, organizational commitment, and trust. The key factors in engagement are such as alignment of employees toward strategy; enabling employees to have the capability to engage themselves; and creating the sense of engagement. This multi-faceted nature of employee engagement is well captured by the Employee Engagement Consortium at Kingston University. The researchers say that: 'fundamental to the concept of employee engagement is the idea that all employees can make a contribution to the successful functioning and continuous improvement of organizational processes (Ye, 2022). Engagement is about creating opportunities for employees to connect with their colleagues, managers and the wider organisation. It is about creating an environment where employees are motivated to want to connect with their work and really care about doing a good job.

Efficiency

Efficiency is a term that recently has come to the forefront of the scientific world. As the world struggles to accommodate the enormous growth in population and to manage the distribution of resources, the effort to make things more efficient has become increasingly more relevant (Haines 2019). We talk about fuel efficiency in cars and energy efficiency in our homes. We strive to learn how to efficiently collect data, use space, recycle goods, and run a business. Nevertheless,

somewhere in this vast search for efficiency we seem to have overlooked the most powerful set of systems and tools we have, ourselves.

If we are truly in pursuit of maximum efficiency, we need to look at how efficient we are as a social whole. Most people wake up each morning with several things on their minds, but efficiency is typically not one of them (Gigna, 2021). Instead, each day our thoughts and rituals are predetermined by our basic instinctual imperative to survive. According to renowned psychologist, Abraham Maslow, we have a general 'hierarchy of needs' we must fulfil. Our first concern is immediate survival, so we must find something to eat and drink. Then, we must prepare for our future survival and the numerous factors that go into sustaining our lives.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Firms' experience employees dissatisfied with their jobs, they are thought to perform less and more prone to absenteeism. Organizations project these in their employment directly and or indirectly through allied services to the business. It is therefore imperative that the welfare of the staff working in these companies are given paramount importance by both managers and the firms' stakeholders as a whole. For many employees today both male and female lives are becoming more consumed with a host of family and other personal responsibilities and interests in addition to demands of the workplace.

The venture sector is now under pressure to ensure decent working conditions for their employees. The relationship between labour relationship practices and the management in the venture sector is not a bed of roses. Therefore, considering the previous studies ideology, none considered the role of Job Rotation, compressed work and flex time in enhancing employee performance. This is because Flexible working relationship in an organizations working arrangement relative to time, working location and pattern of working. part time, shift work, compressed work hours and Job Rotation are considered in this present study, and it is gap or a departure in this current study.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between flexible work arrangement and employee performance of food and beverage firms in Rivers State. Other specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the relationship between job rotation and employee's effectiveness in food and beverage firms in Rivers State.
2. Determine the relationship between job rotation and innovativeness in food and beverage firms in Rivers State.
3. Determine the relationship between job rotation and efficiency in food and beverage firms in Rivers State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The researcher developed the following research questions to guide the conduct of the study

1. What is the relationship between job rotation and employee's effectiveness in food and beverage firms in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between job rotation and innovativeness in food and beverage firms in Rivers State?

3. What is the relationship between job rotation and efficiency in food and beverage firms in Rivers State?

METHODOLOGY

The study research design was cross-sectional survey design which is descriptive in nature. The reason being that cross-sectional survey research design is greatly utilized in the administrative or management research because of the complication that exists between study variables which is most often concerned with the behaviour of social entities, institutions and group characteristics. Hence, this study as a quasi-experimental design study is descriptive in nature, adopted the cross-sectional survey approach to determine the relationship between flexible work arrangement and employees' performance. The population of this study consist of Five Hundred and Eight (508) employees of the fifteen (15) food and beverage firms in Rivers State of Nigeria that are registered with NAFDAC . The researcher adopted a stratified sampling method because the number of the total management employees of each selected listed consumer goods manufacturing companies have been grouped (strata). The researcher made use of simple random technique to select the samples contained in each group (stratum). The main instrument applied was questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed following standard guidelines for questionnaire design. The initial component of the questionnaire embraced the demographic background of the respondents, while the second component constituted 24 item-questions answered in Likert scale format, which measured relevant constructs. The data relating to the subject area of consideration were analyzed using relevant statistical tool, such as Descriptive Statistics to observe the characteristics of the variable and Spearman Rank Correlation since the researcher intends to delineate the level of relationship between independent and dependent variable, therefore, this tool is appropriate for the analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1 Job Rotation

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	SA	A	D	SD	Total
(A)	Work rotation determines the employee commitment in terms of time in hours worked	61	79	44	40	224
	Work rotation determines the amount of effort in man hours used by employee to achieve organization success	62	78	35	49	224
	Expanding the number of hours of giving out services is done through work rotation hence influences the number of hours an employee can perform his/her tasks	59	93	37	35	224

	Work rotation helps in reducing absenteeism in as per number of days an employee attends work	52	100	42	30	224
	Total	234	350	158	154	896
	Averages	58	88	40	39	224
	Percentages	26	39	18	17	100

Source: Field survey 2024.

From the table, 234(26%) strongly agree, 350(39%) agree, 158(18%) and 154 (17) strongly disagree on job rotation.

Table 2 Innovativeness

S/N	DESCRIPTION	SA	A	D	SD	Total
(E)	Does Innovativeness on policy of a firm improve the Job Rotation techniques	64	91	37	32	224
	Technological Innovativeness has it impacted on Job Rotation or work shift	58	96	37	33	224
	Does Innovativeness on compressed work affect the employees performance	49	109	34	32	224
	Innovativeness on employees attitude to work trigger improved flex time	43	107	40	34	224
	Total	214	403	148	131	896
	Averages	53	101	37	33	224
	Percentages	24	45	16	15	100

Source: Field survey 2024.

From the table 2 214(24%) strongly agree, 403(45%) agree, 148(16%) disagree and 131 (15%) strongly disagree on innovativeness.

Table 3 Efficiency

S/N O	DESCRIPTION	SA	A	D	SD	Total
(F)	Increased productivity is influenced by number of actual patients compared to desired number in the organization.	65	90	34	35	224
	Customer satisfaction is influenced by the number customer care staff in the organization.	55	96	39	34	224
	Job satisfaction is linked to the number of days an employee attends work	50	101	39	34	224
	Employee turnover is influenced by the number of employees moving into and leaving the organization in a given period	53	98	40	33	224
	Total	223	385	152	136	896
	Averages	56	96	38	34	224
	Percentages	25	43	17	15	100

Source: Field survey 2022.

From the table 3 223(25%) strongly agree, 385(43%) agree, 152(17%) disagree and 136 (15) strongly disagree on efficiency.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the findings, discussions are made on the study: Job rotation has a positive insignificant relationship with employee effectiveness of food and beverage manufacturing firms. This could be due to lack of monitoring the employees at their duty post and Job rotation has a positive insignificant relationship with innovativeness of food and beverage manufacturing firms in Rivers State. This could due to unrelated events of Job Rotation to Innovativeness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the empirical analysis, the researcher concluded that there is a positive insignificant relationship between job rotation and employees' effectiveness of food and beverage firms in Rivers State and there is a positive insignificant relationship between job rotation and innovativeness of food and beverage firms in Rivers State. There is a positive insignificant relationship between job rotation and efficiency of food and beverage firms in Rivers State..

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The managers and directors of food and beverage firms should not undermine the work arrangement of their staff.

2. Were possible, compressed work arrangement should be adopted to enable the employees have full day off from work.
3. There should be time spelt out for employees flex time in order to expose them to side skills that make them efficient in carrying out their works.

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